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Unheard Voices of Mothers with Sexually Abused Children: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

This study was designed to explore and understand the common experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father. It is a qualitative approach using multiple case study research design. The study was conducted to selected Shelter House of Sexually Abused Children specifically Incest case. Three (3) mothers referred by Laura Vicuña Foundation; four (4) from Palayan City Home for Girls; and three (3) mothers from NCR referred by Guidance Counselors with the case of Incest. The criteria of selection were limited to mothers whose daughter was sexually abused by their biological father. The ages of the children are between 7 and 16 years old who are still living with their mothers whose ages range from 40-59 years old. The study revealed that the experiences before, during and after the disclosure, were described as painful, unbelievable, and unexpected by the mothers. The indicative themes directly helped the mothers realize the difficulties they encountered in the arms of their own biological fathers. This represents how the indicative themes of time, person and event leads to the discovery of the abuse which leads to positive responses of being strong for their daughters as represented by the results. However, during the disclosure of the abused, it was revealed that there is an evident vision of a mother in anger and pain knowing that their daughters were abused by their biological fathers, a mother in confusion who cannot easily manage and understand the entire scene of the abuse, a mother in a jealous state since her daughter confided that in the long run of the abuse, she felt the sexual urge with his father. More so, a mother in shame is also visible for her daughter as well as her entire family because they may be put into conviction by the people around them and a mother of strength who never doubted their heart of sending her husband to jail and let him pay for his crime. Finally, the aftershock or final disclosure was also a painful revelation among daughters who were sexually abused by their own biological fathers. As such, mothers are being their daughter's shoulder to cry on, a cure to their aching hearts, a protective shield against harm, a genuine friend, and a hero to win the battle for their abused daughters. The mother and daughter respectively signify their continuous determination to move on with life and be a positive will of helping their daughters to survive from the abuse. Thus, the result became the basis in the development of a TOOLKIT FOR MOTHERS OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN. This would be used by the guidance counselors, in helping mothers to cope up with the trauma, community and shelter house catering sexually abused children, and most specially, mothers who are the second victim of the abuse.

Keywords: *traumatic experiences, mothers, discovery of sexually abused children, father*

Introduction

Sexual abuse of children and adolescents is a significant global public health issue, violating human rights and causing severe physical, sexual, reproductive, and mental health consequences. Health-care providers disproportionately report cases of such abuse (WHO, 2017). One form of sexual abuse that incites great concern is the acts of raping that occur within a family circle popularly known as incest. Incest could simply be defined as a sexual relationship between close relatives, which is jurisdictionally illegal and/or considered as a social taboo (Beard, Stroebel, O'Keefe, Harper-Dorton, Griffee, & Young, 2015).

Incest rape, originating from the Latin word incestus, is a forced sexual activity between family members. In the Philippines, fathers and uncles are common perpetrators, with 99% of victims being girls. The rape occurs at home, often when parents are away, and can last for years (Gutierrez, N. (2017). Incest is a social issue often neglected and underreported, making it difficult to prosecute due to complex social issues.

Victims often suffer silently and are reluctant to report to authorities due to societal blame, embarrassment, and fear of family institution breakdown. Children are often the victims, making discovery difficult and causing prolonged misery and emotional scarring. From 2011-2016, DSWD served 2,770 incest victims out of 7,418 sexual abuse victims, with majority being girls aged 14-17, with some cases under 5 years old.

Mothers play a crucial role in their daughters' recovery from sexual abuse, and understanding their experiences is essential for developing effective treatment strategies. This can help reduce distress and improve the recovery of the victimized girls. Research on mothers of sexually abused children by their biological father is limited, leading to insufficient knowledge on counseling approaches and the extent of victimization experienced by these mothers. This study aimed to describe the experiences of mothers before, during, and after disclosure of abuse and develop an intervention program for mothers. The research suggests that mothers are victimized, compromised, and traumatized due to their daughters' sexual abuse. Whether it is the husband or the child, mothers are still working through how to deal with the current circumstances. The responsibility of caring for the children in shelters for sexually abused children falls on them, but there are some issues that they are unable to handle, particularly the effects of the abuse on the child's wellbeing. Concern over children's safety is shared by parents, professionals, and others, and it is made even more challenging and alarming by the alarmingly high number of cases that are reported every day.

The main purpose of this study is to explore and understand the common experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father and to describe the experiences of mothers before, during and after the disclosure.

Understanding the experiences of mothers whose daughters have been sexually abused by their biological father can provide new insights into trauma and mother recovery. This investigation can help identify common problems and coping practices, allowing mothers' subjective experiences to be more prominent. Mothers go through a similar grief process as those grieving the loss of a loved one.

This study is beneficial to mothers of sexually abused daughters to understand themselves better, process their trauma, stand with the rights of their children, maintain the trust, and regain confidence for the new and productive life ahead. For the Shelter house of sexually abused, DSWDs, and other NGOs who are handling the sexually abused children, they may understand and be equipped with the proper process of handling children who were sexually abused by their parents.

For the counselors, so that they can design a program for those who are sexually abused by their father and enable to deliver counseling strategies exclusively for mothers and children who experienced being sexually abused within the family and make them understand and process their trauma to rebuild their lives and continue their new life ahead.

Thus, the result became the basis in the development of a **TOOLKIT FOR MOTHERS OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN**. This would be used by the guidance counselors, in helping mothers to cope up with the trauma, community and shelter house catering sexually abused children, and most specially, mothers who are the second victim of the abuse.

Research Objectives

The main purpose of this study is to explore and understand the common experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father and to describe the experiences of mothers before, during and after the disclosure; Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Describe the experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father; and
2. Develop a Toolkit for Mothers of Sexually Abused Children.

Literature Review

According to Willingham, E. (2007), mothers of sexually abused children experienced the same trauma as their daughter. Feeling guilty for not protecting their child, they may reconstruct the events of their children's trauma and intrusively experienced same images. In fact, the mother has been blamed for the sexual abuse more so that the perpetrator in many cases.

On the study of Thapa, T. (2018), mothers had average level of awareness regarding girl child abuse. However, a significant proportion of mothers still lacks a good level of awareness, and it was found significantly associated the age, ethnicity, educational status, type of family, age at marriage and number of children. A nationwide study of such kind using qualitative tools as well as conducting awareness raising activities focusing on girl child abuse and sexual abuse in girl child is recommended.

Williams (2011) cited that the family's contextual environment significantly influences adolescent reaction to sexual abuse. Each systematic level had significant variables. School engagement was the only significant variable. Parental social support and parental educational levels were significant exosystemic variables.

Fabre (2016) cited that mother's response to child sexual abuse depends on her relationship with the perpetrator. It was found out that mother's support was either missing or provided, but changeable more frequently when the perpetrator was her spouse or a current sexual partner. Possible explanations are more or less speculative that there is an emphasized maternal existential emotional dependence on the offender.

Young daughters who take on the mother role are usually emotionally overwhelmed because they are behaving in ways that are beyond their developmental capacity. Not only are their own emotional needs not being met because they're being emotionally neglected, but they are overexerting themselves mentally, emotionally and physically, often without any emotional support. If they are also taking on the role as the father's sex partner, this is, obviously, extremely damaging and exacerbates the emotional trauma. Often the mother in the role reversal dynamic, without realizing it, lacks empathy for the daughter. The mother might lack empathy because she hasn't dealt with her own history of being in a role reversal with her mother. This is a complicated dynamic and, as illogical as it might seem, this does necessarily mean that the mother in this situation does not love the daughter. The lack of empathy usually means that the mother is unable or unwilling to see the damage being done, despite the love she might feel for the daughter, because she doesn't know how to be nurturing and her own unfulfilled emotional needs are so great. The mother also might not know how to express love to her daughter because her own mother never expressed it to her (Ferraro, 2015).

The road between a little girl and her mother is supposed to be a one-way street with support flowing consistently from the mother to the daughter. It goes without saying that little girls are totally dependent on their mothers for physical, mental and emotional support. However, one of the many faces of the Mother wound is the common dynamic in which the mother inappropriately depends on the daughter to provide her with mental and emotional support. This role-reversal is incredibly damaging to the daughter, having long-range effects on her self-esteem, confidence and sense of self-worth (Bethany Webster, 2020).

There is little research on mothers of sexually abused children resulting in a gap in research and literature. The result is insufficient knowledge regarding the needs and counseling approaches for mothers of sexually abused children by their biological father. It is not known to what extent mothers of sexually abused children feel victimized as a result of their daughters' sexual abuse. It is necessary and highly recommended that the study of sexual abuse expands to include a focus on the pain of both victims, the children and the mothers. Due to the limited of research about mothers of sexually abused children by their biological father, this study focused on how sexual abuse affects mothers of sexually abused children. The scope of this study focused on the unheard voices of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father. The outcome of the study was to describe the experiences of mothers before, during and after the disclosure of abuse and to develop an intervention

program for mothers of sexually abused children by their biological father. The research suggests that mothers are victimized, compromised and traumatized as a result of the sexual abuse of their daughters.

Mothers are key individuals in their sexually abused daughters' recovery. Therefore, it is important to examine how the sexually abused children' trauma also impacts the mother. Both the mother and the daughter are at risk for a high level of distress that could decrease the mother's parenting. Exploring mothers' feelings, reactions and experiences after the sexual abuse of their children helps health practitioners professionals determine appropriate intervention for the mothers. The Toolkit is designed specifically for mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father. Life is difficult for mothers after the disclosure of their child's abuse and few resources are available to support them. They have no supportive family or friends. They have limited knowledge about sexual abuse and there is a struggle on how to understand what has happened to their child. Most mothers of sexually abused children say that they need and want to help after the disclosure. This Toolkit is designed to be a source of practical information about sexual abuse that offers support and resources to navigate the journey of healing and support to mothers of sexually abused children. The related studies and literature focused on the victim and the perpetrator. Mothers of sexually abused children were not given the attention as well as the trauma that they experienced after the disclosure. It is important to study mothers' responses for several reasons. First, if mothers do, indeed, suffer significantly from their children's disclosures, they should be acknowledged as victims and given appropriate psychiatric care. Second, because of the well-documented association between parental psychopathology and children's mental health, maternal distress may impede children's recovery following disclosure. The mother's distress affects her ability to provide maternal support. The disclosure of a child's sexual abuse constitutes a major life crisis with chronic, long-lasting effects. Her ability to support the abused child is an important factor in the child's well-being and resolution of symptoms. Thus, the well-being of mothers is very important since they will be the source of strength for their children to continue to go on with their lives.

The researcher used this framework as the foundation in eliciting Mother's Relationship with the husband, Relationship with the Daughter before, during and after the disclosure of the abuse. The Mother's Cognitive Functioning, Emotional Functioning, Perception of the World, and Moral Perception were also considered as the foundation background to reveal the unheard voices and described their experiences as a second victim of the abuse.

The In-depth interviews using structured interview, interview with the Barangay, Police station, DOH, DSWD, Commission on Human Rights, Observations with field notes, video recorder, and diaries of the mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father described the relationship with the husband and daughter before, during and after the disclosures as well as the coping practices of mothers when they discovered the incest. "A TOOLKIT FOR MOTHERS OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN" was developed to provide with specific, practical answers to many frequently asked questions, to guide and assist mothers to understand the journey of their children and to heal their own wound, and to provide options for directions in effectively navigating the very difficult path of their lives as a new therapy in the context of the Filipino culture that can be used to address the trauma of mothers whose daughter was sexually abused by their biological father.

Methodology

This study attempts to explore and understand the common experiences of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father. The experiences of mothers before, during and after the disclosure and what are the coping practices of mothers of sexually abused children was analyzed and interpreted by coding and themes by the researcher.

It is a qualitative approach using multiple case study research design. The study was conducted to selected Shelter House of Sexually Abused Children specifically Incest case. Three (3) mothers referred by Laura Vicuña

Foundation; four (4) from Palayan City Home for Girls; and three (3) mothers from NCR referred by Guidance Counselors with the case of Incest. The criteria of selection were limited to mothers whose daughter was sexually abused by their biological father. The ages of the children are between 7 and 16 years old who are still living with their mothers whose ages range from 40-59 years old. The study used a questionnaire in Filipino and English to gather data on mothers' experiences of sexual abuse, including disclosure, and used observation, checklist, recorder, field notes, and archival records from various government agencies.

The DSWD Central Office approved a researcher to conduct interviews with participants from NCR, Region 4A, and Region 3, including mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father, with attached research request forms and questionnaires. Before the data was analyzed, the researcher transcribed all interviews. The researcher wrote transcription of the interviews straightforwardly, omitting the non-verbal interactions, and included in the field notes. The audio recorder was also used as backup for the interviews for the accuracy of the data collected.

The researcher conducted an interview at a confidential location, including a Guidance Office for a victim's mother at Ramon Magsaysay High School, and referred parents to family homes. The interview allowed for detailed questioning and debriefing after trauma. The study utilized a multiple case study design, analyzing data through cross-case analysis. Data was gathered through interviews, field notes, and other documents. Preliminary notes were used to identify recurring patterns and themes. Thematic analysis was conducted using Braun and Clarke's step-by-step guidelines, highlighting salient and similar themes across all cases.

The researcher organized data from shelter houses to classify participants and identify categories describing mothers' experiences of sexual abuse. They also explored unheard voices as second victims. Recurrent themes were identified to understand participants' experiences during disclosure and identify the most significant themes.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher obtained ethical clearance from the PNU Educational Policy Development and Research Center, permission from selected schools, and written informed consent from participants. Participants were assured of confidentiality, anonymity, and privacy. A structured interview was used, with recorded responses and time management to cover all questions. The interview was conducted at a safe location, such as a Guidance Office for the victim's mother at Ramon Magsaysay High School. The researcher coordinated with a psychologist for debriefing after the trauma. Feedback on the research findings was crucial, with a summary sent to all participants and social workers involved.

Result and Discussion

1. Describe the experiences of mothers whose daughters were sexually abused by their biological father.

1.1. The Discovery - Before the Disclosure

Figure 1. *Abuse Discovery Indicative Pattern*

The indicative theme which is time the mothers' discovery of the abuses varies, ranging from two months to ten years but most of them discovered the abuse for a long period. In terms of the indicative theme of a person specifically prescribed that the abuse was discovered from various people namely the victim herself, the mother of the victim and from another person. Relative to time, age of the victims may also be uncovered; age of the

victims ranges from five to nine years old and the helplessness during the situation was expressed by the victims. Regarding the indicative theme of event, the abuse was unraveled through daughters confiding to their mothers, teachers and friends informing the mothers of the abuse, actual event of the abuse discovered by mothers themselves as well as relatives expressing their grief over the incident to the victim's mother. Relative to this, the abuse was described as painful, unbelievable, and unexpected by the mothers.

These indicative themes directly helped the mothers realize the difficulties they encountered in the arms of their own biological fathers. The solid arrows represent how the indicative themes of time, person and event lead to the discovery of the abuse which lead to positive responses of being strong for their daughters as represented by the solid line. The discovery scenario may be capsulized by the pattern below.

1.2. Divulging the Abuse (During the Disclosure) Mothers upon knowing the abuse may be represented by Pattern 2.

Figure 2. Status upon knowing the abuse

The arising themes from the transcripts painted various portraits of mothers. An evident vision is a mother in anger and pain knowing that their daughters were abused by their biological fathers, a mother in confusion who cannot easily manage and understand the entire scene of the abuse, a mother in a jealous state since her daughter confided that in the long run of the abuse, she felt the sexual urge with his father. More so, a mother in shame is also visible for her daughter as well as her entire family because they may be put into conviction by the people around them and a mother of strength who never doubted their heart of sending her husband to jail and let him pay for his crime.

Figure 3. Link after discovering the Abuse

Pattern 3 vividly presents the solid link between the mothers and daughters, yet there are instances that the daughters wanted to detach themselves, still their bonds with their mother are tighter. The circular figure encapsulating the mother and daughter respectively signifies their continuous determination to move on with life while the solid line connecting them represents the bond tightened by the abusive incident. A solid line leading to the thrust the mothers wanted to offer their daughters was encapsulated in the box solidly connected by an arrow representing the mothers' positive will of helping their daughters survive from the abuse.

Figure 4. The Agony of the abused

Pattern 4 presents the two main characters in the actual abuse, the father and the daughter as represented by the two boxes at the end and at the tip of the arrow. The abusive fathers directly and solidly caused agony to their daughters by abusing them and making them victims of rape. Specifically, the deduced agonies are agony of threat to loved one's life, agony of possible disbelief, agony of fear, agony of physical pain, agony of emotional pain, and agony of sexual pain.

Figure 5. *Stimuli of Abuse*

Pattern 5 presents the primary stimuli of abuse based on the deduced themes. The first box pertains to the main theme identified called the stimuli of abuse that are directly connected by solid arrows which pertains to a compact identification of the two main stimuli of abuse. These stimuli include father as abuse stimulus which includes the vices, evil inclination and sexual urge and mother as abuse stimulus which includes physical absence in rearing their daughter and inability to suffice husband's sexual urge.

Figure 6. *The father as an abuser*

Pattern 6 presents the direct description of the fathers who raped their daughters as contained in the first box directly connected by a solid arrow which represents a compact description of these fathers pointing to the descriptions deduced listed inside the second box namely symbol of pain, agent of fear and icon of selfishness.

Figure 7. *Family Relationship after Unveiling the Abuse*

Pattern 7 presents the direct description of the family relationships as contained in the first box directly connected by a solid arrow which represents a compact description of the family relationship challenge to the descriptions deduced listed inside the second box namely symbol birth of hatred, state of unforgiveness, family separation, losing respect and trust

Figure 8. *Healing the Bruises of the abuse*

Pattern 8 presents on how the victims undergo healing and reinvent themselves as an individual. The internal remedy includes healing the emotions, setting hopeful goals and realizing forgiveness while the external remedy

includes setting a new environment, comforting the victims and safekeeping the child to a place far from the incident venue.

Healing the mother-victim relationship and re-establishing a sense of trust is critical to the victim's recovery. It is important to understand that, as mothers provide security, and trust is re-established, attachment increases. The mother-victim attachment bond is one of the most critical predictors of reduced consequences to sexual abuse. It is also important that mothers understand the betrayal bond that may be established between the abuser and the victim.

Develop “A TOOLKIT FOR MOTHERS OF SEXUALLY ABUSED CHILDREN”.

The basis of the toolkit was the outcome of the study conducted to identify the needs and strategies for handling mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological fathers. It is observed in our laws and society that sexually abused children have support programs and policies to assist them in coping, healing and recovery with their trauma but when it comes to the well-being of mothers there are no existing guidelines to support them. In this toolkit, you will discover strategies and guidelines in handling cases of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological fathers which will help in providing interventions that will help them live better lives.

Analysis

In conclusion, mothers experienced the same trauma as their daughter when the disclosure was revealed. Knowing that the age of the victim was ranging from five (5) to nine (9) years old, it was very painful, unbelievable, and unexpected on the part of the mothers. The abuse was discovered from various people namely the victim herself, the mother of the victim and from another person and the discovery of the abuses ranging from two months to ten years and most of them discovered for the long period. Mothers experienced shock and significantly distressed upon learning about their children's victimization especially when the abuse was a long time ago and they blamed themselves for not acknowledging the signs that their children were raped.

Mothers also had mixed emotions during the disclosure, mother in anger and pain knowing that their daughters were abused by their biological fathers, a mother in confusion who cannot easily manage and understand the entire scene of the abuse, a mother in a jealous state since her daughter confided that in the long run of the abuse she felt the sexual urge with his father. More so, a mother in shame is also visible for her daughter as well as her entire family because they may be put into conviction by the people around them and a mother of strength who never doubted their heart of sending her husband to jail and let him pay for his crime. However, after the painful revelation of abused, mothers still portrayed their importance as the protector of their children. They still wanted to give justice on the crime that their husband committed. Mothers wanted to protect their children as a cure to their aching hearts, a shoulder to cry on, a protective shield against harm, a genuine friend and a hero to win the battle against their biological fathers, and positive will of helping out their daughters survive from the abuse.

Finally, the researcher came up with the development of a Toolkit for Mothers of Sexually Abused Children. This Toolkit is designed to be a source of practical information about sexual abuse that offers support and resources to navigate the journey of healing and support to mothers of sexually abused children. This can also be used by guidance counselors, shelters of sexually abused children and other communities that handle the same cases. It also addresses the need to be informed and to be familiar with the issue of sexual abuse to help battle the detrimental effects deeply corrupting young innocent victims and to eventually safeguard them from further abuse.

Conclusion

It is evident that the role of mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father is very important in the healing process of the victim. The mother should protect the child towards the abuser (biological father). It is imperative that the mother accepts the fact that abuse occurred, believe the child's disclosure, decide to take action to protect the child (e.g., separate from abuser), and recognize that the child is at continued risk of abuse. Without these, the mother may be unable to maintain a safe home and protect the child. Revictimization is a serious potential threat to the child's safety.

Mothers experience a range of emotions and reactions following the disclosure that their children have been sexually abused. A mother may go through emotions associated with the stages of anger, confusion, jealousy, shame and strength. However, after the disclosure, the mother needs to be strong to provide a positive will of helping their daughters survive from the abuse. Lastly, the healing process involves the internal remedy includes healing the emotions, setting hopeful goals and realizing forgiveness while the external remedy includes setting a new environment, comforting the victims and safekeeping the child to a place far from the incident venue.

Finally, the unheard voices of Mothers whose children were sexually abused by their biological father can be addressed by using/adapting the Toolkit for Mothers of Sexually Abused Children. It addresses the need to be informed and to be familiar with the issue of sexual abuse to help battle the detrimental effects deeply corrupting young innocent victims and to eventually safeguard them from further abuse.

This Toolkit is designed to be a source of practical information about sexual abuse that offers support and resources to navigate the journey of healing and support to mothers of sexually abused children. This can also be used by guidance counselors in Basic Education and Tertiary level as a tool in developing a Counseling Program for mothers of learners/students who are experiencing abuse in the family; Shelters of Sexually abused children; Social workers, and Centers for Women of Abused as a supplementary materials in creating a program for mothers; Family Counselors, Mothers journeying with daughters/son; Barangay Community, and Teachers; This can also be used as a tool for developing supplemental materials about Self- Healing from forgiveness, Regaining Self-Esteem and Self- confidence, Family (Role of Parents and Guardians Safety; Legislation Policies on Women Empowerment;

It is also recommended to consider this toolkit as part in planning and developing of curriculum for Gender and Development (GAD) to include the results of this research; to integrate the empowerment and awareness of mothers and learners on the curriculum development since the Comprehensive Sexuality Education was already done. This was an additional reference material in the integration of subject in Homeroom Guidance specifically, on Personal-Social domain with a topic of learning about the process of healing; Integration in ALS Curriculum about Gender and Development; Curriculum in Grade 10 under Contemplative Issues, among others; and integration in the Good Manners and Right Conduct (GMRC/VE) and Values Education Curriculum.

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